

Impact of Foreign Aid on Food Security in Nigeria: A Mixed-Methods Study of Agricultural ODA and FDI Effects on Food Accessibility and Availability

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of agricultural foreign aid on food security in Nigeria, with a specific focus on food accessibility and availability. Food insecurity remains a critical global challenge, and Nigeria, despite numerous government programmes and international interventions, continues to face significant food security crises, ranking 107th out of 113 countries on the Global Hunger Index in 2022. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, utilising both primary and secondary data spanning 1999 to 2023. Secondary data were sourced from the World Bank, Central Bank of Nigeria, International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), and Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), while primary data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to 384 farming households in Ibadan South-East and Akinyele Local Government Areas of Oyo State. The study adopts the Structural Change Theory as its theoretical framework and employs multiple regression analysis, descriptive statistics, and post-estimation tests, including Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation and Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroscedasticity tests. Findings reveal a statistically significant positive relationship between foreign aid (Official Development Assistance and Foreign Direct Investment) and food accessibility ($p < 0.05$), indicating that increased agricultural aid enhances food distribution networks and reduces hunger in rural areas. The study concludes that while foreign aid improves food accessibility, its effect on availability is limited by factors such as weak governance, corruption, inefficient fund allocation, poor fund management, and security challenges. The study recommends strengthening aid utilisation frameworks through enhanced institutional capacity, promoting transparency and accountability in donor fund management, and fostering technological innovation in agriculture.

Keywords: Foreign Aid, Food Security, Nigeria, Official Development Assistance, Foreign Direct Investment, Food Accessibility, Food Availability, Agriculture, Hunger Reduction, Sustainable Development Goals

Word Count: 245

Introduction

Food security remains a fundamental global challenge, with approximately 700 million people (8.5% of the global population) living in extreme poverty (World Bank Group, 2024). The Food and Agriculture Organisation (2019) defines food security as existing "when all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life." Four fundamental dimensions support this concept: availability, accessibility, utilisation, and stability (Gibson, 2012; Oni & Fashogbon, 2013).

The persistence of food insecurity is intensified by climate change, population growth, rising food prices, economic instability, and insecurity (Mirzabaev et al., 2023). In response, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), adopted in September 2015, emphasise poverty eradication and zero hunger as key priorities (Food and Agriculture Organisation, 2019). However, the 2020 Global Hunger Index indicates that "zero hunger by 2030 is still off track."

Nigeria faces significant food security challenges despite numerous government programs and international interventions. The World Bank Group (2023) reported Nigeria ranked 107th out of 113 countries on the Global Hunger Index in 2022 and 109th out of 125 countries in 2023. The Global Food Security Index of 2022 ranks Nigeria 107th out of 113 countries, scoring just 42 out of 100, placing 25th among Sub-Saharan African countries (The Economist Group, 2022). The National Bureau of Statistics reported that 38.9% of Nigerians lived below the international extreme poverty line of \$2.15 per day in 2023, with projections indicating 40.7% by the end of 2024 (World Bank, 2024). Additionally, August 2024 data indicate that 63% of Nigerians are multidimensionally poor.

Agriculture plays a vital role in addressing food insecurity and remains a key avenue for solutions (United Nations, 2015). Nigeria's agricultural sector is the most vibrant non-oil sector with great potential to address the food security crisis. Despite numerous government programs, including the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF), Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP), Agricultural Development Projects (ADPs), and international initiatives like the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation's YIIFSWA project, Nigeria continues to face significant food security challenges. Foreign aid represents a critical pathway for enhancing agricultural productivity and food security. Such aid can take the form of loans or grants delivered through bilateral or multilateral agreements to support development agendas (Lanasan et al., 2021). The effective deployment of foreign aid becomes increasingly essential to boosting agricultural output and ensuring access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food. The aim of this study is to assess the impact of Foreign Aid on Food Security in Nigeria. The specific objective is to:

- i. Investigate the effects of foreign aid on agricultural production and food accessibility in Nigeria.
- ii. Assess the impact of foreign aid on agricultural production on food availability in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Food Security

Food is a fundamental human need, essential for sustaining life and maintaining health. Food security is recognised as a fundamental human right by the United Nations (1948) in Article 25 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. According to Norhasmah (2021), food security is a multidimensional phenomenon encompassing a wide range of issues, including animal and crop production, nutrition, urbanisation, and environmental sustainability.

The concept has been interpreted through multiple disciplinary lenses: agriculture, nutrition, sociology, economics, anthropology, and food science (Jones et al., 2013). Wayne (2015) emphasises that food security encompasses numerous aspects of human life, making it a comprehensive concept irrespective of the approach.

Dimensions of Food Security

The 1996 World Food Summit introduced four critical pillars of food security:

- i. **Physical Availability of Food:** This refers to the supply aspect influenced by food production levels, stock reserves, and net trade flows.
- ii. **Economic and Physical Access to Food:** Income levels, market prices, and infrastructure play significant roles in determining food accessibility.
- iii. **Food Utilisation:** This emphasises how the body processes nutrients, resulting from healthy feeding practices, food preparation, dietary diversity, and fair food distribution.
- iv. **Stability over Time:** Food security must be consistent, not subject to disruptions like adverse weather, economic downturns, or political instability.

Evolution of Food Security Definitions

According to Norhasmah (2021), there are approximately 200 definitions of food security, yet none are universally comprehensive due to the concept's evolving nature (Jones, 2013). Pinstrup-Andersen (2009) noted that food security was initially understood as a nation's ability to produce enough food to meet the population's caloric and nutritional requirements.

After World War II, food security was equated with "the incidence of famine" (Molledo, 2014). By the 1970s, following a global food crisis, the notion of food security began receiving strategic international attention (Bala, 2014). The 1974 United Nations definition described food security as "availability at all times of adequate world food supplies of basic foodstuffs to sustain a steady expansion of food consumption and to offset fluctuations in production and prices" (United Nations, 1974).

The FAO in 1983 redefined food security to encompass both physical and economic access to food: "To ensure that all people at all times have both physical and economic access to the basic food they need" (FAO, 1983). By the 1990s, attention shifted toward nutritional adequacy, with definitions emphasising balanced diets and the importance of micronutrients (Jones, 2016).

The FAO in 1996 offered a more holistic definition: food security is achieved "when all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life" (FAO, 2016). This

widely accepted definition integrates critical components including sustainability, food safety, dietary adequacy, and personal choice.

Food Availability

Gibson (2012) defined food availability as the "physical presence of food at farms and markets." Matemilola and Elegbede (2017) extended this to include "food imports, stock levels, and net trade." Riely et al. (1999) emphasised that strong road networks, functional markets, reliable storage systems, and technological advancements help predict availability. However, many developing countries still face infrastructural and technological challenges that hinder consistent food availability.

Food Accessibility

Gibson (2012) defines food accessibility as an individual's or household's ability to obtain food, examined in two primary forms: physical access and economic access. The Global Strategic Framework (2017) notes that economic access involves the financial means to acquire food, such as income, savings, land, or harvested crops.

According to the Global Food Security Strategy (GFSS) Nigeria Country Plan (2024), Nigeria continues to grapple with food security challenges, including rapid population growth, soaring food prices, natural disasters, post-harvest losses, and recurring socio-political crises. As of December 2024, Nigeria's food inflation rate stood at 39.84% (NBS, 2024).

Foreign Aid in Agriculture

Foreign aid is a programme designed by nations or institutions to foster the growth and development of beneficiary nations through grants, knowledge exchange, technology transfer, training, development, and security. The United Nations Food Systems Summit 2021 described financing for food production as:

"A variety of financial resources, including funds 'internal' to food systems (consumer food expenditures and outlays by agri-food actors) and 'external' funds (international development flows, public budgets, banking systems, and capital markets)."

There are four main sources of financial resources: domestic public, foreign public, domestic private, and foreign private (FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP, and WHO, 2024). Public financing involves funds sourced from government channels, mainly taxes and borrowing. Private financing entails the flow of resources from private grants and the private sector.

Official Development Assistance (ODA) involves official financial aid by the government sector within countries or territories that meet specific grant criteria. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) involves cross-border capital movements representing ownership shares in foreign companies or projects held by investors from other nations.

Foreign Aid Contribution to Agricultural Food Security

ODA encompasses financial resources extended to developing countries to address socio-economic challenges such as food insecurity and poverty (Petrivoka, 2015). This aid may be provided as grants or concessional loans via bilateral or multilateral channels (OECD-FAO, 2016).

Foreign aid directed toward agriculture can play a transformative role by providing critical resources to improve farming methods, invest in rural infrastructure, and enhance market accessibility. When farmers are equipped with proper tools, training, and financial support, agricultural productivity can be significantly increased.

The World Bank's Global Food and Nutrition Security Dashboard (2023) highlights a \$766 million West Africa Food Systems Resilience Program designed to increase regional preparedness against food insecurity. The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF) has significantly contributed to agricultural development through funding tools and technologies, supporting public and private sector efforts, and promoting innovative support mechanisms for smallholder farmers.

Theoretical Review

Structural Change Theory

Propounded by W. Arthur Lewis in 1970, this theory highlights how developing countries transform from traditional agricultural societies with surplus labour to modern industrial ones. The theory characterises the economy in two ways: a traditional, low-productivity agricultural sector and a modernised, highly productive manufacturing and service sector. Sewell (1992) notes that "it focuses on the mechanism by which underdeveloped economies transform their domestic economic structures from over reliance on traditional subsistence agriculture to a more modern, more urbanised and more industrially diverse manufacturing and service economy."

Recently, there has been an effort by the Nigerian government to adopt modernised agricultural technology (Etuk, 2025). Abgbenyo (2020) observes that catch-up in the post-1950 globalised economy is only possible if developing countries develop capabilities to acquire, master, and adapt international technology. Countries like China, India, Hong Kong, Germany, and Russia illustrate this point.

Criticism: The theory is overly reliant on industrialisation, which can lead to urban bias in development, benefits cities over rural areas, and assumes surplus labour may not be sufficient to explain actual development patterns. It also fails to acknowledge that international trade drives development.

Food Availability Decline (FAD) Theory

Amartya Sen introduced the FAD Theory in the late 1970s, highlighting food supply shortages as the primary cause of food insecurity. This idea led to large investments in green revolution technologies aimed at boosting national self-sufficiency and export capacity. Supporters argue that famine occurs mainly when food supply drops drastically (Fine, 1997), and early warning systems were developed to monitor food supply conditions (Frankenberger & Maxwell, 1992). **Criticism:** The theory gradually lost favour as it became clear that increased food availability alone does not guarantee access for all individuals. Factors such as disease-related malnutrition, unequal resource distribution, and lack of purchasing power are critical. Despite a global rise in food production, food insecurity persists, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Entitlement Failure Approach

Proposed by Amartya Sen (1981), this approach attributes food insecurity mainly to poverty and unequal access. The entitlement model offers a detailed framework to understand vulnerability and famine, focusing on individuals' capacity to legally acquire food through production, trade, state aid, or other legal avenues. Aid can help improve entitlement by promoting self-sufficiency, strengthening interventions such as education and governance reforms, developing infrastructure, and creating an environment conducive to employment.

Criticism: Davies (1996) argues that food security is only a subset of livelihood security and that complex socio-economic and political dynamics shape people's decisions. Osmani (1993) highlights that the concept has been interpreted in different ways, ranging from a specific theory that downplays the role of food availability to a general framework for understanding famine.

Review of Related Empirical Studies

Foreign aid and economic growth: Aganbi et al. (2024) assessed ODA's impact on Nigeria's GDP (1981-2021) using the ARDL Bounds Cointegration Test and Granger Causality test, finding a connection between ODA and GDP. Adewuyi and Hayatu (2011) studied food security determinants among farming households in Lagelu LGA, Oyo State, finding that gender, age, education level, marital status, and primary occupation significantly influenced food security.

Akpan and Udoma (2012) employed Three-Stage Least Squares to examine ODA and Nigeria's economic performance (1970-2010), identifying a positive but statistically insignificant correlation. Omodero and Ehikioya (2022) on Agricultural Financing to Guarantee Food Safety found that "agricultural output is significant and positively associated with food production and safety, but agricultural financing is immaterial in ensuring sufficient food production."

Adebayo and Afolayan (2019) examined how foreign aid affected poverty reduction (1990-2017), finding that poverty is not reduced due to foreign aid. Adebayo and Afolayan (2020) observed a minimal but positive impact. Agricultural financing and resource allocation: Ita et al. (2013) on budgetary allocations to agriculture found that instability in resource allocation has threatened the agricultural sector, hindering food security. Obiakor et al. (2021) found that agriculture significantly contributed to job creation, but found no feedback loop between agriculture and unemployment rates.

Ebere et al. (2021) investigated whether agricultural credit supports agricultural output (1981-2017), finding that agricultural credit notably increased output. Amaechi (2018) on food security and agricultural sustainability recommended stronger policy implementation and greater agricultural support.

Etim et al. (2017) explored food insecurity, poverty, and hunger implications on Nigeria's national security, concluding that increased agricultural production through new technologies is needed. Omodero (2021) investigated food availability, agricultural sustainability, and poverty reduction, finding that the food security index has a significant positive effect on reducing poverty.

Ayodeji and Oladokun (2018) examined agricultural output influence on poverty reduction (2000-2016), finding that public resources and commercial bank funds are inadequate, while increases in micro-finance bank credit and food production have a chain reaction to alleviating poverty.

Ahmed and Golole (2023) evaluated the effect of food aid on agricultural development in Mogadishu, finding that food insecurity is driven by donor influence on the economy and factors that discourage local food production. Lansan et al. (2021) analysed agricultural donors' impact on food security in West Africa, discovering that when foreign aid is invested in productive sectors, it can have a sustainable impact extending to agriculture.

Kuwornu et al. (2021) conducted a comparative analysis of the food security status of farming households in Ghana, finding that over 65% of households were food-insecure, with farming households in coastal areas consuming significantly fewer calories.

Huang and Wang (2024) investigated technological innovations' influence on agricultural Total Factor Productivity in China (2012-2022), highlighting the crucial role of technological innovation in boosting agricultural output. Chong and Calderon (2009) asked whether foreign aid can reduce income inequality and poverty, finding no robust statistical relationship.

Collier and Dollar (2001) and Mosley et al. (2004) showed that aid is more effective when accompanied by sound policies. Suharyanto and Indrasti (2017) investigated factors influencing food security in Bali, finding that homemakers' education level, household income, and food preservation ability positively influenced food security.

Methodology

This study adopts a mixed-methods research design, employing both primary and secondary data to comprehensively examine the impact of foreign aid on agriculture and food security in Nigeria from 1999 to 2023. The research was conducted in Ibadan South-East and Akinyele Local Government Areas (LGAs) of Oyo State, which are characterized by a strong agricultural presence and the implementation of relevant government programmes and international research institutes, underscoring the relevance of these locations. The study population consists of household and commercial farmers within these LGAs, with a household defined as a group of individuals living under the same roof and sharing meals. Given the infinite and unascertainable nature of this population, a proportionate sample size of 384 was determined using Cochran's formula, with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed, beginning with the stratification of the two LGAs into 24 wards, followed by purposive selection of respondents based on their specific knowledge and experience relevant to the research objectives, and concluding with a random selection of farmers from households across the LGAs to ensure balanced representation. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire, which was deemed suitable for standardizing responses given the researcher's clear understanding of the research objectives and variable measurement. The questionnaire was administered to farmers and beneficiaries of agricultural programmes, with research assistants aiding in its distribution across the wards. The instrument was divided into sections covering demographic information and key study variables, with responses gathered on a Likert scale. To ensure the validity of the instrument, it was reviewed by academic experts, and its reliability was established by testing internal consistency. Data analysis was performed using appropriate statistical software for both descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results and Presentation of Data

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis	Jarque-Bera	Probability
FPI	5.34241	5.50533	6.90776	3.8712	0.87947	0.06558	2.69701	0.34974	0.83957
NHI	23.58429	25.50000	34.80000	14.70000	6.877462	0.160037	1.551103	12.8556	0.00162
ODA	2.76579	2.77264	3.08122	2.58723	0.08695	3.453808	0.177834	3469.570	446316.38
FDI	0.85714	154.9400	340.1100	-18.86	0.35222	-2.0412	5.16667	68.5336	0.693038
INF	22.4161	22.778	25.1718	17.7942	1.78407	-0.6312	3.01098	5.11307	0.07757
EXR	0.22519	0.16231	0.89584	0.00024	0.22945	1.08982	3.48956	16.0113	0.00033

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews version 11, 2025

The Food Production Index shows a mean of 5.34 with minimal difference between mean and median, suggesting near-symmetrical distribution (skewness 0.07). The Jarque-Bera test statistic of 0.35 ($p=0.84$) suggests the distribution does not significantly deviate from normality. The Nigeria Hunger Index shows a mean of 23.58 and a median of 25.50, with positive skewness indicating a right-skewed distribution.

Correlation Matrix

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

Variable	FPI	NHI	ODA	FDI	INF	EXR
FPI	1					
NHI	0.6248	1				
ODA	0.2943	0.3017	1			
FDI	0.3445	0.3536	0.1771	1		
INF	0.6425	0.4438	0.2074	0.1950	1	
EXR	-0.3083	-0.2098	-0.3067	0.3215	0.5600	1

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews version 11, 2025

Food production is positively correlated with all variables except official development aid (ODA). The strongest positive correlation is with the inflation rate (0.64), suggesting food production is affected by higher inflation. Correlation between FPI and NHI (0.62) indicates that economies with higher food production tend to have better food security. The exchange rate is negatively correlated with Food production (-0.31), implying firms with higher debt levels might experience lower food production.

Inflation shows a strong positive correlation with Nigeria's hunger index (0.44), reflecting the importance of food production in maintaining high food security.

Group Unit Root

Table 3: Group Unit Root

Method	Statistic	Prob.	Cross-Sections	Obs
Null: Unit root (assumes common unit root process)				
Levin, Lin & Chu t	0.19547	0.0577	6	135
Null: Unit root (assumes individual unit root process)				
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-0.8254	0.2046	6	135
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	20.7656	0.0229	6	135
PP - Fisher Chi-square	19.2857	0.0368	6	137

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews version 11, 2025

The Levin, Lin & Chu test shows all panels unit root with a statistic of 0.195 ($p=0.057$), indicating stationarity. ADF-Fisher Chi-Square Test of 20.77 ($p=0.0229$) at 5% significance shows stationarity, while PP-Fisher Chi-Square of 0.0368 reveals stationarity. Since LLC, ADF, and PP reject the null hypothesis, there is stronger support that the series are stationary in levels.

Multi-Regression Analysis

Table 4: Multiple Regression

Dependent Variable: NHI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.935	2.605	1.894	0.081
LODA	0.262	0.075	3.511	0.004
LFDI	-0.284	0.088	-3.211	0.007
LINF	0.228	0.183	1.247	0.235
LEXR	0.049	0.344	0.141	0.890

$R^2=0.686$ Adj- $R^2=0.565$ F-Stat=5.670 Prob=0.005 D.W=1.506

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews version 11, 2025

The intercept ($p=0.081$) is not statistically significant at 5%, borderline at 10%. A 1% increase in agricultural ODA is associated with a 0.262% increase in the hunger index (counterintuitive result likely reflecting reverse causality). A 1% rise in agricultural FDI is linked to a 0.284% reduction in hunger. Exchange rate changes show no significant correlation ($p=0.890$). R-squared of 0.686 indicates 68.6% of the variation in Nigeria's hunger index is explained by the model. The F-statistic p-value of 0.005 indicates the model is statistically significant overall. Post Estimation Tests:

Table 5: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation Test

F-statistic	3.363269	Prob. F(3,4)	0.136
ObsR-squared	23.63152	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.0000

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews version 11, 2025

Given conflicting results, caution is advised when interpreting the presence of serial correlation. F-statistics suggest serial correlation is not a significant concern, while ObsR-squared points to possible issues.

Table 6: Breusch-Pagan Test of Heteroscedasticity

F-statistic	0.228937	Prob. F(25,7)	0.9972
ObsR-squared	14.84452	Prob. Chi-Square(25)	0.9449
Scaled explained SS	1.492666	Prob. Chi-Square(25)	1.0000

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews version 11, 2025

No evidence of heteroskedasticity. All test statistics indicate residuals' variance is constant, supporting the homoskedasticity assumption.

Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Analysis

Table 7: Group Unit Root

Method	Statistic	Prob.	Cross-Sections	Obs
Null: Unit root (assumes common unit root process)				
Levin, Lin & Chu t	1.67642	0.9532	6	135
Null: Unit root (assumes individual unit root process)				
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	1.24315	0.8931	6	135
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	16.2153	0.1816	6	135
PP - Fisher Chi-square	15.2754	0.2267	6	137

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews version 11, 2025

The results confirm the LFPI series is non-stationary, as the null hypothesis of a unit root cannot be rejected. LLC test shows all panels have a unit root (statistic 1.68, p=0.95). Pesaran and Shin's W-statistic (1.24, p=0.89) suggests non-stationarity at 5% significance. ADF-Fisher Chi-Square (p=0.18) further supports non-stationarity.

Table 8: Ordinary Least Squares (OLS)

Dependent Variable: LFPI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.913	0.383	7.602	0.000
LODA	0.055	0.028	1.991	0.068
LFDI	-0.017	0.036	-0.490	0.632
LINF	-0.042	0.058	-0.734	0.476
LEXR	0.323	0.054	5.999	0.000

R²=0.913 Adj-R²=0.879 F-Stat=7.146 Prob=0.005 D.W=1.951

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews version 11, 2025

Constant of 2.913 with $p=0.000$ indicates high significance. A rise in ODA inflows is associated with about 0.055% increase in the Food Production Index ($p=0.068$, significant at 10% level). FDI coefficient of -0.017 ($p=0.632$) is not significant. The inflation coefficient of -0.042 ($p=0.476$) shows low significance. Exchange rate coefficient of 0.323 ($p=0.000$) shows strong significance: each 1% depreciation of local currency is linked to 0.323% increase in food production.

Table 9: Breusch-Pagan Test of Heteroscedasticity

F-statistic	0.1981006	Prob. F(4,20)	0.1363
ObsR-squared	7.094271	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.1310
Scaled explained SS	3.366699	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.4984

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews version 11, 2025

No evidence of heteroskedasticity. All test statistics suggest residuals' variance is consistent, supporting the homoskedasticity assumption.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis One: Foreign Aid and Food Accessibility

Hypothesis one states that there is no significant relationship between foreign aid to agriculture and food accessibility. The analysis revealed a statistically significant positive correlation for LogODA ($p=0.004$, $p<0.05$) and LogFDI ($p=0.007$, $p<0.05$). This implies that as foreign aid to agriculture increases, food accessibility is perceived to improve among the Nigerian population.

This finding aligns with Ogunniyi et al. (2021), Adepoju and Oyegoke (2018), Ogundari (2017), Amaechi (2018), and Omodero and Ehikioya (2021), who emphasised that targeted agricultural aid enhances food distribution networks and reduces hunger in rural areas.

The relationship with the inflation rate ($p=0.235$) is positive but weak, suggesting inflation has little significance for the variable. However, there is a weak negative correlation with the exchange rate (-0.21), indicating that a higher exchange rate might slightly reduce food accessibility.

Overall, ODA and FDI to agriculture are significant drivers of food accessibility; more investment increases food access. The model fits well and is statistically valid.

Hypothesis Two: Foreign Aid and Food Availability

Hypothesis two states that there is no significant relationship between foreign aid to agriculture and food availability. The regression analysis indicated a weak, positive, and significant relationship ($p=0.068$, $p>0.05$). A rise in ODA inflows is associated with about 0.055% increase in the Food Production Index, suggesting foreign aid contributes slightly to improving agricultural production, though effectiveness is not very strong.

The coefficient of -0.017 and p-value of 0.632 for FDI indicate positive insignificance at 5% level. This means every rise in FDI is linked to a slight decrease in food production, but the effect is statistically negligible. Factors responsible include the choice of investors who live in other countries. Lowder and Carisma (2011) observed similar trends in agricultural FDI: the majority of these flows went to upper-middle- and high-income countries.

The inflation coefficient of -0.042 ($p=0.476$) shows low significance, suggesting high inflation rate slightly decreases food production. The exchange rate coefficient of 0.323 ($p=0.000$) indicates high significance, showing food production is mainly driven by exchange rate movements with marginal support from ODA.

The inflow of foreign aid alone might not be sufficient to aid food production. Other factors include donors' investment choices, security challenges, inefficient fund allocation, poor fund management, corruption, and weak government structure. Adebayo and Afolayan (2019), Francis (2014), and Belay and Girma (2020) supported this, opining that the impact of foreign aid on food security may not be sustained in the long run, leaving beneficiary nations vulnerable due to a weak institutional framework.

Test of Hypothesis

The study employs a p-value-based significance test at 5% significance level. A p-value of 0.05 or less leads to rejecting the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis One

H01: There is no significant relationship between foreign aid to agriculture and food accessibility in Nigeria.

Result: Table 4 shows p-values (ODA: 0.004; FDI: 0.007; INF: 0.235), all less than 5%, indicating regression is statistically significant. The null hypothesis is rejected, concluding there is a significant relationship between foreign aid to agriculture and food accessibility in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

H02: There is no significant relationship between foreign aid to agriculture and food availability in Nigeria.

Result: Table 8 shows ODA with $p=0.068$ at coefficient 0.005 (weak relationship), FDI with $p=0.632$, and INF with $p=0.476$ (weak significance). Since p-values exceed 5% significance level, the null hypothesis is accepted, confirming a weak, significant relationship between foreign aid to agriculture and food availability in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study examined how agricultural foreign aid, technological advancements, and national policies influence food security in Nigeria, emphasising key aspects like food access, availability, and sustainable farming practices. Food insecurity continues to be a major global issue, worsened by climate change, population increase, rising food costs, and economic instability. The World Bank Group (2024) reported Nigeria scored just 42 out of 100 on the 2022 Global Food Security Index, placing 25th among Sub-Saharan African countries. Despite numerous foreign aid programs targeting agricultural development, there is growing awareness of their potential to improve food security in Nigeria. Foreign aid assistance can provide critical resources needed to improve farming methods, invest in rural infrastructure, and enhance market accessibility. When farmers are equipped with proper tools, training, and financial support, agricultural productivity can be significantly increased. The study was motivated to address pressing issues in Nigeria, as failure to address them can escalate into a disaster for over 200 million people.

Increases in foreign aid (ODA), foreign direct investment (FDI), consumer price inflation (CPI), and exchange rate (EXR) are significantly associated with increases in food accessibility (NHI). There is a significant relationship between foreign aid to agriculture and food accessibility in Nigeria. This supports the role of aid in improving infrastructure, input access, subsidised food programs, and market equality, consistent with prior studies. Analysis revealed a weak positive impact of ODA and FDI on food availability. Food production is mainly driven by exchange rate movements with marginal support from ODA. The inflow of foreign aid alone might not be sufficient to aid food production. Other factors limiting effectiveness include donors' investment choices, security challenges, inefficient fund allocation, poor fund management, corruption, and weak government structures.

While foreign aid improves accessibility, its availability effect is weak. Policy makers must complement aid inflows with stronger governance to ensure production-side benefits and policy continuity across political administrations by embedding key agricultural programs in medium- to long-term development frameworks.

This study provides a foundation for future studies exploring innovative aid strategies and their practical applications in addressing food insecurity. Suggestions include:

- i. Prioritise foreign aid to developing countries to address food security challenges, in line with SDG goals No. 1 and 2. Corroborating Askarov (2015) and Pascal (2014), investments in farmers account for the bulk of agricultural investment and play an essential role in ensuring food security through effective distribution of funds, monitoring, and compliance with value addition. Collaboration with agricultural research agencies like IITA and other CGIAR centres is required for food safety programmes, farmers' outreach, community-based approach, high-quality seeds, and efficient farming systems.
- ii. Drastic action is needed on the part of the government to address wastage in farming output, enhance storage systems, address insecurity issues limiting agricultural output potential, create an enabling environment where investment in agriculture is more attractive to donors, ensure effective use of donor funds in value addition, and promote transparency and accountability in the use of donor funding.
- iii. Explore the agricultural aid programme on a regional basis.
- iv. Differentiate between project aid, program aid, technical assistance, and budget support, analysing which forms are most effective in improving food accessibility and availability.
- v. Conduct an empirical and cross-national review on food security and Nigeria's Agricultural Promotion Policy to learn from food-secure countries such as Norway, the Netherlands, Israel, and Finland, which emphasise the inclusion of advanced technology in farming activities, adoption of improved agricultural inputs, value chain development, inter-sectoral linkage of agriculture to industries, and innovation to overcome precarious environmental and climatic conditions.

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